

ISic3623

I.Sicily inscription 3623

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Melita

Place of origin (modern)

Malta

Provenance

Rabat, catacomb of St. Agata, hypogeum no.5

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Rabat, Museum of St. Agata, inventory S179

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645696

EDCS 59500347

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2010.0616

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 59.1084

Rizzone, V.G. 2009. Iscrizioni giudaica e cristiane di Malta. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigrafik*. 168: 202-208. At 206-207 no.4 ph

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3623. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388849>